

Synthesis of some new oxovanadates containing two hetero atoms

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The conditions of formation, preparation and formulation of three new triheteropoly oxovanadates have been conducted by pH-metry, thermometric titrimetry, chemical and atomic emission spectroscopic analyses. The compounds have been characterised by X-ray diffraction, thermogravimetry and IR studies.

Preparation of mixed triheteromolybdophosphovanadic acids¹ and existence of $[\text{PMo}_{11}\text{VO}_{40}]^{4-}$, $[\text{PMo}_{10}\text{V}_2\text{O}_{40}]^{5-}$, and $[\text{PMo}_9\text{V}_3\text{O}_{40}]^{6-}$ anions in solution phase² have already been reported. The catalytic and industrial applications of these mixed triheteropoly compounds have also been reported³. The present communication reports the preparation of sodium, ammonium and guanidinium salts of the anion of the type $[\text{ZYV}_{11}\text{O}_{36}]^{9-}$, where Z = Co, Ni; Y = Te.

Results and Discussion

The conditions of formation of $\text{Na}_9[\text{CoTeV}_{11}\text{O}_{36}].24\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $(\text{NH}_4)_9[\text{CoTeV}_{11}\text{O}_{36}].30\text{H}_2\text{O}$, and $[\text{C}(\text{NH}_2)_3]_9[\text{NiTeV}_{11}\text{O}_{36}].28\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were carried out by pH measurements. The suitable pH range at which the compounds can be formed was found to be 3.3–3.8. Exact amounts of reactants required for the formation of these compounds, derived from pH-metry, were corroborated by thermometric titrimetry⁴ as discussed earlier⁵.

The metal constituents were estimated by standard gravimetric methods⁶ and the results were corroborated by inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectroscopy, colorimetry and atomic absorption spectra. The position and assignment of main IR bands and various modes of water molecules^{7,8} are listed in Table 1.

The differential thermal studies⁹ confirmed that the gradual loss of water of crystallisation started at 328 K and complete dehydration took place at 645 ± 20 K. The anionic cage decomposed at above 688 ± 20 K in all cases. From the thermograms, volatilization of the higher oxides of metal was found to take place above 873 K. The decomposition of the anionic cage was also confirmed by the insolubility of the heated samples and the IR studies at this stage showed the absence of expected bands due to different modes of water molecules.

The X-ray powder diffraction¹⁰ using $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 1.5412$ Å) of $\text{Na}_9[\text{CoTeV}_{11}\text{O}_{36}].24\text{H}_2\text{O}$ showed the d -value as 18 corresponding to the interplanar distance 11.8 Å. The 100 point d -corresponds to the d -value of 8.7 Å. The density of the compound was determined by floatation method using carbon tetrachloride-bromofom mixture.

The approximate molecular weight of the compounds were determined by modified cryoscopic studies using $\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4.10\text{H}_2\text{O}-\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4-\text{H}_2\text{O}$ transition system. The experimental molecular weights (calculated values in the paranthesis) for $\text{Na}_9[\text{CoTeV}_{11}\text{O}_{36}].24\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $(\text{NH}_4)_9[\text{CoTeV}_{11}\text{O}_{36}].30\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $[\text{C}(\text{NH}_2)_3]_9[\text{NiTeV}_{11}\text{O}_{36}].28\text{H}_2\text{O}$, were 2000.4 (1961.78), 2079.4 (2024.93) and 2305.65 (2366.84), respectively.

Table 1. IR spectral data (cm^{-1}) of heteropolyoxovanadate

Compd.	$\nu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$	$\delta_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$	ν_{NH}	$\pi_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$	$\nu_{\text{Te-O}}$	$\nu_{\text{M-O}}$	$\nu_{\text{M-O-M}}$	$\nu_{\text{M'-O}}$
$\text{Na}_9[\text{CoTeV}_{11}\text{O}_{36}].24\text{H}_2\text{O}$	3390	1665	—	590	1005	925 875 810	730 650	435
$(\text{NH}_4)_9[\text{CoTeV}_{11}\text{O}_{36}].30\text{H}_2\text{O}$	3435	1655	1410	610	995	935 870 800	705 665	405
$[\text{C}(\text{NH}_2)_3]_9[\text{NiTeV}_{11}\text{O}_{36}].28\text{H}_2\text{O}$	3430	1620	1390	625	985	940 890 790	715 675	445

Experimental

The compounds used were of AnalaR grade. The solutions were prepared in distilled water. The metals were estimated using ARL 3410 atomic absorption spectrophotometer, and C, H and N using Coleman analyser. The IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer, the thermal analyses by a NETZSCH STA-409 analyser and the X-ray diffraction data on a Unicam Weissenberg instrument.

Sodium 11-vanadotellurocobaltate : Cobalt chloride (1.07 g, 4.5 mmol) in aqueous solution (25 cm³) was added slowly to aqueous solution (30 cm³) of telluric acid (1.035 g, 4.5 mmol). This solution was added in small quantities (about 2 cm³) each turn with brisk stirring to aqueous solution (150 cm³) of sodium vanadate (6.1 g, 50 mmol) at buffered pH 3.33. The mixture was warmed on a water-bath for 2 h followed by refluxing for 4 h. Its volume was then reduced to about one-third and left undisturbed in a desiccator. Yellowish brown crystals appearing after 4 days were dried and crystallized from ethanol (yield 4.82 g) (Found : Na, 10.38; Co, 3.06; Te, 6.68; V, 28.86; H, 2.48; O, 48.54. Na₉[CoTeV₁₁O₃₆].24H₂O⁸ calcd. for : Na, 10.55; Co, 3.00; Te, 6.50; V, 28.56; H, 2.45; O, 48.94%).

Ammonium 11-vanadotellurocobaltate : An aqueous solution (50 cm³) containing cobalt nitrate (1.980 g, 6.80 mmol) was added slowly with constant stirring to telluric acid (1.565 g, 6.81 mmol) solution (40 cm³). The mixture was warmed on a water-bath with stirring for ~0.5 h. This solution was added in small installments (2 cm³) to ammonium vanadate (8.775 g, 75 mmol) dissolved in water (200 cm³) with stirring. The mixture was again heated on a water-bath for 1.5 h and then refluxed for 2.5 h. The content was reduced to about 50 cm³ and the resulting brown crystals that appeared after 3 days were air-dried and washed with ethanol (Found : N, 6.01; H, 4.88; Co, 2.81; Te, 6.49; V, 26.99; O, 52.82. (NH₄)₉[CoTeV₁₁O₃₆].30H₂O calcd. for : N, 6.22; H, 4.74; Co, 2.91; Te, 6.30; V, 27.67; O, 52.15%).

Guanidinium 11-vanadotelluronickelate : Stoichiometric amounts of aqueous solutions of nickel chloride (1.07 g, 4.5 mmol), telluric acid (1.06 g, 4.6 mmol) and sodium

vanadate (6.1 g, 50.02 mmol) were taken and the sodium compound was prepared in the same way as adopted for sodium 11-vanadotelluronickelate. The guanidinium salt was then prepared by metathesis using sodium salt (4.0 g, 2.164 mmol) solution (20 cm³) and guanidinium hydrochloride (1.24 g, 12.98 mmol) solution (10 cm³). The mixture was heated on a water-bath for 1.5 h and left overnight. Greenish grey compound obtained was washed with ether and air-dried (Found : C, 4.32; N, 15.03; H, 4.37; Ni, 2.22; Te, 5.99; V, 23.91; O, 44.16. [C(NH₂)₃]₉[NiTeV₁₁O₃₆].28H₂O calcd. for : C, 4.56; N, 15.98; H, 4.65; Ni, 2.48; Te, 5.39; V, 23.68; O, 43.26%).

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References

- 1 G A Tsigdinos and C J Hallada, *J Less-Common Met*, 1974, 36, 79
- 2 R I Maksimovskaya and M A Fedotov, *Dokl Akad Nauk SSSR*, 1978, 240, 117
- 3 M H Tunic, P W Smith and V H Holsinger, *J Thermal Anal*, 1997, 49, 795, T Kasprzycka-Guttman, M Jorosh-Jorszewska and G Litwinienko, *Thermochim Acta*, 1995, 250, 197, E M McCarron and A W Sleight, *Polyhydron*, 1986, 5, 129
- 4 H J V Tyrell and A F Beczer, "Thermometry Titrimetry", Chapman and Hall, London, 1968
- 5 S K Roy and G C Bhattacharya, *J Indian Chem Soc*, 1975, 52, 1051, 1977, 54, 638, *Indian J Chem*, 1977, 1, 41
- 6 N Borochoy, E J Watchtel and D Bach, *Chem Phys*, 1995, 76, 85, A I Vogel, "Text Book of Quantitative Analysis", Longman Green, London, 1960
- 7 G A Tsigdinos, *Top Curr Chem*, 1978, 76, 1
- 8 M T Pope, "Heteropoly and Isopoly Oxometallates", Springer Verlag, Berlin, 1983
- 9 R C Mackenzie, "Differential Thermal Analysis Fundamental Aspects", Academic, London, 1970, S K Roy and P K Sinha, *J Indian Chem Soc*, 1998, 75, 477
- 10 "X-Ray Powder Data File", Inorganic sets 1-10, A S T M, U S A, T J R Weakley, *Struct Bonding (Berlin)*, 1974, 18, 131